

CREDIT CARD ACCESSIBILITY OF EMPLOYEES OF GOVERNMENT ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS IN DAET, CAMARINES NORTE: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the credit card accessibility of employees in government academic institutions in Daet, Camarines Norte, aiming to provide a basis for intervention. Utilizing a descriptive and correlational research design with purposive sampling of 100 respondents from the Department of Education (70%) and Camarines Norte State College (30%), the study employed percentage frequency distribution, weighted mean, Somer's Delta, and Contingency coefficient for data analysis. The findings revealed that most respondents were female, aged 31-40, married, with some master's units, earning below Php 30,000 monthly, permanently employed as teachers, using credit cards 1-3 times a month, and had been users for less than a year. Credit usage was rated highly accessible, while benefits/advantages and terms of credit were mostly accessible. Significant relationships were found between age and marital status with credit card accessibility levels. The primary problems identified were limited merchant options, susceptibility to fraud, and high interest rates. Based on these results, an intervention plan was proposed to enhance credit card accessibility and optimize its benefits for these employees.

Keywords: *Credit card, accessibility, credit usage, benefits and advantage, terms of credit, credit card users*

INTRODUCTION

In previous years, most customers felt safe, secure, and comfortable with the traditional method of making purchases or paying for any transaction with cash, which many merchants have adopted. Today, however, there is a significant shift from conventional to online or digital banking systems, providing consumers with convenient access to various financial and non-financial transactions through their smartphones anytime, anywhere, and without the need to carry large amounts of cash. Consequently, to determine the relevance of various factors affecting government employees' decision to apply for and use credit cards, the study will look at the accessibility of credit cards to them. Despite the benefits of having a credit card, some employees opt not to have one.

Based on research undertaken by the Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco in the United States, credit cards made 28 percent of all payments in 2021. This is the highest level since the study's launch in 2016, proving that credit cards are gaining ground over cash or other means of payment. Credit card payments increase proportionately to family income, rising to 34 percent for families earning \$100,000 to \$149,999 and 44 percent for those earning more than \$150,000. Despite a growing trend of credit card usage in developing economies, only 14 percent of adults reported using one on average. China, Russia, Turkey, and Ukraine in Europe and Central Asia, as well as Argentina and Brazil in Latin America and the Caribbean, were the exceptions. In these economies, the proportion of adults borrowing with a credit card but not through a loan from a financial institution or mobile money provider ranged from close to 40 percent in the three European and Central Asian economies to approximately 50 percent in China and approximately 60 percent in the two Latin American and Caribbean economies (Pokora, 2023).

According to the Asia Report 2022, credit card penetration in Thailand, Indonesia, and Vietnam remains ten percent or less, while 47 to 67 percent of the population uses mobile payments. Cambodia, Myanmar, Laos, Vietnam, and the Philippines are the five Asian nations with the fewest credit card consumers. According to their report, they prefer to conduct ordinary transactions with cash or debit cards. However, according to the Philippines Cards and Payments Market Report, the Philippines continues to be a cash-dependent society with a sizable unbanked population. Debit cards are the most prevalent form of a payment card, with approximately seven percent of adults possessing a credit card. In addition, according to the Global Economy report, the average percentage of individuals aged 15 and older with a credit card ranges from 1.94 percent in 2017 to 8.09 percent in 2021 (World Bank Gender Data Portal, 2022).

Prior to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, developing nations increasingly utilized cashless transactions as one of their primary payment methods, such as purchasing necessities on online marketplaces, acquiring food online, and conducting financial transactions online. However, because of the COVID-19 virus-induced mobility restrictions and people limiting their physical contact with various goods (such as physical currency) out of fear of contracting the virus, there is a surge in demand for contactless financial services that traditional banking alone cannot satisfy. It prompted a pivot to

digital finance that will profoundly transform the Philippine financial industry and usher in a new era. Adopting the accelerated digital transformation process will promote financial inclusion, enhance the overall user experience, and provide everyone in the country with benefits such as convenience and efficiency (Advantages and Disadvantages of Credit Card, 2023).

As a result, the Philippines is among the Southeast Asian markets that have experienced significant shifts toward non-cash transactions, with a 30 percent increase in transaction volume between 2016 and 2021 and a 9 percent increase in card transactions. According to a report by the World Bank Organization, this volume of non-cash financial transactions is expected to more than triple by 2031 (Asia Annual Bank Report, 2022).

Customer engagement has become digital. Every digital customer's journey begins with a seamless, highly digital customer acquisition, resulting in the onboarding of consumers following near-real-time credit assessment and decision-making. This is an overview of the background of the credit card-issuing industry. This instance exhibits the value of credit cards despite the increasing number of contactless payment applications in the Philippines that offer comparable services to consumers. Surprisingly, compared to other contactless payment methods, credit cards continue to be one of the underrated modes of payment (Digital Payments, 2021). Credit cards are an advanced form of payment and one of the most recent types of consumer credit in the world; they enable cardholders to make contactless purchases from merchants and affiliates, facilitating credit card transactions with ease and security. Its contactless feature enables tap-to-pay purchases, while card-not-present transactions are protected by a one-time password (OTP) via the 3DSecure facility. The credit card is also referred to as a borrow write-down card because the cardholder can obtain credit without collateral and mortgage credit and is permitted to spend up to their credit limit. They are not required to pay the total balance during the grace period, and cardholders can replenish their credit funds. Credit cards can expedite transactions and delay cash payments as a form of non-currency payment and credit service. It can be used for emergencies such as cash advances in installments, exceptional service, and rewards on purchases made with a credit card (Argus Advisory Research - Philippines Cards and Payments Market Report, 2020).

Despite the advantages and benefits mentioned above about credit cards, many reports have proven that only a few are availing of the services of credit cards. According to the World Bank report, many countries have low credit card users regardless of the benefits and ease of use. Based on their 2021 report, Nicaragua has the lowest credit card holder with 1.6 percent; following were Paraguay at 2.8 percent, Colombia at 9.8 percent, Bolivia at 10.5 percent, Peru at 11 percent, Argentina 23.3 percent, Brazil 33.3 percent and Canada at which has the most considerable cardholder 83.4 percent (Fontinelle, 2021).

When former President Barack Obama signed and approved the Credit Card Accountability Responsibility and Disclosure Act (also known as the Credit CARD Act) on May 22, 2009, it became the United States of America's most comprehensive modification

of credit card regulations. The CARD Act is a federal law that governs credit card issuers in the United States for more excellent consumer protection as a supplementary measure of the Truth in Lending Act. One of its goals is to safeguard customers from unfair practices credit card companies use. The CARD Act's critical benefits for customers include restrictions on rate increases, fee increases, the elimination of double-cycle billing, prolonged deadlines, and protections for young consumers. On the contrary, the CARD Act does not pertain to the following: uncapped rate increases, interest rate increases, short notice periods, and corporate exemptions (Moore & Thangavelu, 2023).

On the other hand, in the Philippines, the Republic Act No. 10870, known as An Act Regulating the Philippine Credit Card Industry, lapsed into law on July 17, 2016, under Article VI, Section 27 (1) of the Constitution. The Philippine Credit Card Industry Regulation Law regulates all credit card issuers, acquirers, and transactions. The State's policy is to promote the growth of the credit card industry as a crucial tool for ensuring that consumer credit is easily accessible to all Filipinos under the conditions of fair and sound consumer credit practices that are in line with international best practices to promote an effective payments system and to encourage competition and transparency that support effective delivery of credit card services (Alburo and Associates Law Offices, 2022).

The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) through the Monetary Board, in its Resolution No. 55 dated 13 January 2023, approved specific provisions amending the Manual of Regulations for Non-Bank Financial Institutions on the ceiling on interest or finance charges for credit card receivables. The BSP released Circular No. 1098 on September 24, 2020, imposing a 24 percent annual cap for the interest or financing charges on all credit card transactions to reduce the burden on Filipino consumers as they deal with the COVID-19 pandemic. With the publication of BSP Circular No. 1165, banks and credit card issuers may now charge interest or finance charges on all credit card transactions that do not exceed an annual interest rate of 36 percent, except for credit card installment loans, which are subject to monthly add-on rates that do not exceed 1 percent (Ocampo and Sularvo Law Office, 2023).

Studies of customers' behavior towards credit cards have mainly focused on the decisive role of individual demographic characteristics, credit card attributes, and personal perception of credit cards. Some variables affecting bank depositors' application and utilization of credit cards are intention to use, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and the possible risk of using the credit card (Frankel, 2021).

Intention to use is the purpose of the credit card holder and how they will benefit from using the credit card. Perceived ease of use is the extent to which an individual believes that using a specific technology does not require additional effort. People do not always need to carry money to do a transaction. Thus, ease of use should impact the use of credit cards. Perceived usefulness is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his/her performance, while perceived risk refers primarily to consumer subjective expectations for incident losses. Moreover, based on the researcher's initial interview with some government employees, most are hesitant to use

credit cards in their transactions. Some of their reasons are that they avoid the possible fees or charges (like annual fees) for the credit card and are not knowledgeable about or unfamiliar with using credit cards. This situation is also confirmed by the agents and other financial institutions offering credit cards, such as Landbank, BPI, BDO, and Metrobank agents. Based on them, only a few people are availed of the credit card service in Camarines Norte.

Hence, this study aimed to identify the credit card accessibility of government employees in connection with their demographic profile and the variables to be considered. It will measure the level of credit card accessibility in terms of credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit. Likewise, it will show the possible problems encountered when accessing credit card facilities. As well as, to serve as the basis for an intervention plan to improve credit card accessibility for government employees.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to describe the credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions in Daet, Camarines Norte, as the basis for an intervention plan.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of employees of government academic institutions in Daet, Camarines Norte, along:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 age;
 - 1.3 marital status;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 monthly gross income;
 - 1.6 employment status;
 - 1.7 number of times of credit availment; and
 - 1.8 number of years using credit cards
2. What is the level of credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions along:
 - 2.1 credit usage;
 - 2.2 benefits and advantages; and
 - 2.3 terms of credit?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of employees of government academic institutions and the level of credit card accessibility?
4. What are the problems encountered by employees of government academic institutions in accessing the credit card facility along:
 - 4.1 credit usage;
 - 4.2 benefits and advantages; and
 - 4.3 terms of credit?
5. Based on the results of the study, an intervention plan may be recommended to improve the credit card accessibility of employees of government

METHODOLOGY

This study used the quantitative method and employed the descriptive-correlational design. According to Bhasin (2019), descriptive research is a research method that explains the features of the population or phenomena being studied. Thus, the descriptive research method was used because the study searched for answers about the profile of employees in government academic institutions in terms of sex, age, marital status, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, number of times of credit availment, and number of years using credit cards. The study also looked at the respondents' level of credit card accessibility and identified problems that government employees had accessing their credit cards.

It was correlational because the design tested relationships between variables of interest, such as the credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions, by selecting variables, evaluating data, and demonstrating concepts with examples from published literature. According to Creswell (2012), correlation research is a statistical test to evaluate the capacity or direction of two or more variables or sets of data to change frequently. This strategy made use of survey questions to gather data efficiently. Surveys can be beneficial for obtaining detailed information about individuals' experiences, views, and attitudes, enabling real-time insights into respondents' points of view and identifying the extent to which a link exists between two or more measurable variables.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The total population was 1,543 based on the number of government employees in the selected educational institutions in the province of Camarines Norte, according to the latest data received as of October 2023, provided by the concerned agencies: Department of Education - Camarines Norte Field Office and Camarines Norte State College. Due to the Data Privacy Act and Republic Act No. 10870, An Act Regulating the Philippine Credit Card Industry, Sec. 16. Confidentiality of information emphasizes that credit card issuers, their officers, employees, and agents shall keep strictly confidential the data on the cardholder. The researcher, therefore, was unable to determine the sample size or the total number of employees who currently own credit cards. Consequently, the researcher selected respondents using purposive sampling, which is a particular type of non-probability sampling technique. A total of one hundred (100) respondents with existing credit cards were the sample size and were pro-rated based on the total population, which is 70 percent or 70 respondents from the Department of Education and 30 percent or 30 respondents from the CamarinesNorte State College.

Description of the Respondents

This study's respondents were the credit card holders and employees of government academic institutions, including teaching, non-teaching, job order, or contract of service personnel from the Department of Education and Camarines Norte State College. The employees with existing credit cards were the main respondents because

they had the knowledge and experience to answer the survey questionnaire to assess the level of accessibility and problems encountered.

Research Instrument

The primary data collection tool for the research was a structured survey questionnaire; a printed copy was distributed to respondents, and those who preferred to respond online were given an online survey form; the survey questionnaire results were then consolidated. The research questionnaires were divided into four (4) sections and differed based on the details required for the analysis.

The first part gathered the profile of the respondents, including sex, age, marital status, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, number of times of credit availment, and number of years using credit cards. The second part determined the level of credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions in terms of credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit. The third part covered the problems encountered by the respondents. The last part collated the respondents' possible recommendations and proposals for intervention.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the data, the survey questionnaire was presented and reviewed by the researcher's adviser and thesis advisory committee members before the survey was conducted. It underwent requisite checks and validation by experts in the field to ensure the relevance and meaning of the claims and that the data to be collected were vital to the aims and objectives of the analysis. The validation result of the survey questionnaire from five experts in banking, academia, and other credit card providers was interpreted as having high validity with a weighted mean of 4.69.

After checking and scrutinizing the survey questionnaire by the thesis advisory committee and validation by experts, a dry run was conducted to determine the reliability of the survey questionnaire. It was performed with at least 20 government employees from other agencies as respondents. The result of the pre-test was the basis of the consistency of the queries, factors, and measures incorporated in the questionnaire and to identify potential questionnaire errors and verify its validity. The researcher used Cronbach's alpha for the reliability test; the results were 0.918, 0.974, and 0.948, respectively, which indicated excellent internal consistency.

For the survey to proceed, the researcher sent a request letter to the concerned agencies, such as the Camarines Norte State College – Main Campus and the School Division Office – Camarines Norte, for approval to conduct data gathering. Upon approval, the survey questionnaires were handed over to the selected respondents, and those who preferred to answer online were provided with an online survey questionnaire. The data collected were then tabulated and analyzed to produce concrete and accurate results. The researcher guaranteed that the data collected were used exclusively for academic

purposes and held strictly confidential. The college's ethical protocols in research were strictly followed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools used were frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and inferential statistics such as Somer's Delta Correlation coefficient (d) and Contingency coefficient (c).

The statistical methods of descriptive and correlational statistics were primarily employed in the analysis of quantitative results. It is necessary to specify the variables and the usual relationships that developed between and within them to employ descriptive statistics. The percentage and frequency distribution techniques were used to present the profile of the respondents. The weighted mean was used to determine the respondents' answers and distinguish the level of credit card accessibility.

Further, correlational techniques were used to determine statistically when and how closely two variables are associated. Correlation statistics were used to assess whether there is a significant association between the profile of the respondents and the variables along the level of credit card accessibility. By using Somer's Delta Correlation coefficient (d) and the Contingency Coefficient (c). Contingency Coefficient (c) is a non-parametric measure, which means it makes no assumptions about how the data is distributed. It is essential in research because it allows us to assess the strength of a link between two categorical variables and test hypotheses about that relationship. It is a versatile and powerful tool that may be used in a range of situations. Somers' Delta is valuable in research because it allows quantifying the strength of a link between two ordinal variables and testing hypotheses about that relationship. It is a versatile and robust tool that may be used in several scenarios (Agresti, 2013).

RESULTS

Table 1
Sex Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	18	18.0
Female	82	82.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2
Age Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
21-30	24	24.0
31-40	36	36.0
41-50	24	24.0
Above 50	16	16.0

Total	100	100.0
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Table 3
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Marital Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	30	30.0
Married	64	64.0
Widowed	4	4.0
Annulled/Legally Separated	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Educational Attainment

Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
College Graduate	34	34.0
With units in Masters Program	43	43.0
Master's Degree Holder	15	15.0
With units in Doctorate Program	6	6.0
Doctorate degree Holder	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Gross Monthly Income

Amount	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below ₱30,000	54	54.0
₱30,001 - ₱50,00	39	39.0
₱50,001 - ₱100,000	7	7.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Permanent (Teaching)	49	49.0
Permanent (Non-Teaching)	41	41.0
Job Order	4	4.0
Contract of Service	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 7
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Frequency of Credit Card Availment

Frequency of Availment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-3	87	87.0
4-6	6	6.0
7-9	2	2.0
10 and above	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 8
Profile of the Government Employees in Academic Institutions
in terms of Number of Years Using the Credit Card

Number of years	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 1 year	44	44.0
1-5 years	35	35.0
6-10 years	9	9.0
Above 10 years	12	12.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 9
Level of Credit Card Accessibility in Terms of Credit Usage

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Can be used for payment and cash advances	3.37	FA
2. Can be accepted for payment in stores and merchants	3.44	FA
3. Can be used anytime and anywhere	3.15	MA
4. Credit card points earned can be used as a reward and cash back to pay or exchange items	3.16	MA
5. Can be used as a payment alternative for cash payment	3.39	FA
6. Can be used to secure mobile payments and contactless transactions	3.13	MA
7. Can be availed to pay for single purchase items rather than to take a personal loan	3.34	FA
8. Can be used to pay for utilities such as water bills, electric bills, internet, etc.	2.97	MA
9. Can track spending history and transactions	3.33	FA

10.	Can be used for payments in travel bookings	3.24	MA
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.25	FA

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA)

1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)

3.41-4.20 - Agree (A)

1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

Table 10
Level of Credit Card Accessibility in terms of Benefits and Advantages

	Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1.	Can be availed for free interest on installment payments in selected merchants	3.14	MA
2.	Can be a source of additional fund/s in case of emergencies or unexpected situations	3.31	FA
3.	Can offer less cost on cash advances within the credit limit	2.99	MA
4.	Can offer minimal or up to free of charge on an annual fee	2.96	MA
5.	Can offer flexible time frame on repayment of credit balances	3.12	MA
6.	Can offer many ways to earn rewards and bonuses such as cashback, points, vouchers, etc.	3.18	MA
7.	Can give an increase in allowable credit limit and credit score	3.27	FA
8.	Selected items can be availed with discounts and maximize credit usage	3.21	MA
9.	Can offer warranties and protection for users on credit card purchases	3.13	MA
10.	Can cover benefits on travels or special offers such as travel insurance in case of loss, damage, or stolen/fraud	2.89	MA

Overall Weighted Mean 3.12 MA

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA) 1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)
 3.41-4.20 - Agree (A) 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)
 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

Table 11
Level of Credit Card Accessibility in terms of Terms of Credit

	Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1.	Terms and conditions can be readily provided to customers for understanding	3.19	MA
2.	Can provide comprehensive details of card features, interest rates, and rewards	3.23	MA
3.	Can provide the applicable terms, modes of payments, billing cycles, and past due obligation	3.23	MA
4.	Can access or view the statement of account through digital channels (email, SMS, etc.)	3.35	FA
5.	Can provide details on purchase transactions and payments	3.38	FA
6.	Can offer a reasonable interest rate per type of account	3.19	MA
7.	Can provide details on accumulated credit balances and the minimum amount due per billing cycle	3.20	MA
8.	Can secure approval of the credit card application without collateral	3.18	MA
9.	Can provide a list of documents needed for processing credit card applications	3.32	FA
10.	Can provide fast and hassle-free approval of credit card applications	3.14	MA
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.24	MA

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA)
 3.41-4.20 - Agree (A)
 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)
 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 12
Test for Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and their Level of Financial Literacy on Investment Decision

Profile	Credit Card Usage		Benefits and Advantages		Terms of Credits	
	Test Statistics	p-value	Test Statistics	p-value	Test Statistics	p-value
Sex	.164	.427	.159	.461	.110	.749
Age	-.286**	.000	-.195**	.006	-.274**	.000
Marital Status	.440**	.004	.461**	.001	.387*	.040
Highest Educational Attainment	-.092	.268	-.064	.434	-.091	.252
Monthly Gross Income	-.054	.554	-.073	.440	-.055	.551
Employment Status	.225	.803	.216	.844	.283	.467
Frequency of Credit Availment	.132	.387	.063	.701	.165	.300
Number of Years Using the Credit Card	.003	.969	.033	.712	.088	.306

**Correlation is significant @ 0.01 level

*Correlation is Significant @ 0.05 level

Table 13
Problems Encountered by Employees in Accessing Credit Card Facility along Credit Usage

Problems	Frequency	Rank
1. No available card replacement on expired and damaged card	16	5
2. No available Point-of-sale (POS) system	32	3
3. Poor signal and internet connection	40	2
4. Prolonged troubleshooting and unresolved customer complaints	18	4
5. Limited merchant's payment options	52	1

Table 14
Problems Encountered by Employees in Accessing the Credit Card Facility along Benefits and Advantages

Problems	Frequency	Rank
1. Low available credit limit	39	2
2. Susceptible to fraud and unauthorized transactions	43	1
3. No available online payment options (over-the-counter payment)	21	4.5
4. No rewards and warranty on purchase items	22	3
5. High level of salary bracket and income requirements.	21	4.5

Table 15
Problems Encountered by Employees in Accessing the
Credit Card Facility along Terms of Credit

	Problems	Frequency	Rank
1.	Failure to repay account balances or minimum due amount	27	3
2.	High-interest rates and charges	48	1
3.	Fees on missed payments/late payment	46	2
4.	Untimely posting of purchased and payment transactions	17	4
5.	Complicated terms and conditions	13	5

Table 16
Proposed Intervention for Credit Card Accessibility of Employees
in Government Academic Institutions

Problems	Objectives	Strategies	Person Involved	Resources Needed	Expected Outcome
		*Credit Usage			
Poor signal and internet connection	To make sure that merchants are online and avoid inconvenience using credit cards.	Look for merchants that are always online and have uninterrupted internet connections.	Merchants Credit Card Users	Wireless Fidelity (WIFI) Internet Connection	Uninterrupted mode of payment using Credit Cards
Limited merchant's payment options	To identify stores/merchants that accept credit cards. To maximize the utilization of credit cards on payments and purchases.	Inquire with the stores/merchants if they accept credit cards as payments and use them on every purchase. Use credit cards when paying with online stores.	Merchants Credit Card Users	Point-of-Sale System Internet Connection	Availability of payment options for credit cards. Maximize the utilization of credit cards
No available Point-of-Sale (POS) System	To identify stores/merchants that have a POS system to accept payments.	Inquire with the stores/merchants if they have POS systems before purchasing.	Merchants Credit Card Users	Point-of-Sale System Internet Connection	The POS system is available to make payments through credit cards.
		*Benefits and Advantages			
The low available credit limit	To increase the allowable credit limit on credit card account	Improve your credit history by paying the account balance in full per billing cycle and	Credit Card user and issuer	Monthly Billings	Approval of increased credit limit for users

		avoiding late payments. Inquire and negotiate with customer service to lengthen and adjust the payment terms to maximize the credit limit.			
Susceptible to fraud and unauthorized transactions	To avoid becoming a victim of fraud and unauthorized transactions.	Establish strong security passwords and avoid letting someone borrow your credit cards. Watch and subscribe to channels that promote practical tips on using credit cards.	Credit Card Users	Credit card online application Security features	Secured credit card accounts and transactions to have ease of usage
No rewards and warranty on purchase items	To maximize the benefits when using credit cards such as rewards and warranty.	Explore credit card providers that offer generous rewards, bonuses, and warranties. Avail promo that offers free annual fees and minimum charges. *Terms of Credit	Credit Card issuers and users	Credit Card websites	Maximized the rewards system, incentives, and warranty.
High-interest rates and charges	To avoid additional interest rates and charges in billing statements.	Pay the account balance in full per billing cycle and avoid late payments. Consider credit card issuers with low interest rates and no annual fees.	Credit Card Users	Monthly Billings Proof of payment	No additional interest and charges on billing statements
Fees on missed payments/late payments	To avoid additional charges on missed /late payments in billing statements.	Monitor the amount of dues and dates on billing statements. Pay the account balance in full.	Credit Card Users	Monthly Billings Proof of payment	No additional charges on missed/late payments.
Failure to repay account balances or minimum due amount	To avoid the rollover or compounding of account balances and interest charges on the following billing cycle.	Pay the account balance in full per billing cycle and monitor deadlines. Do not swipe the credit card beyond the capacity to pay. Enroll in auto-debit arrangements to ensure on-time payment.	Credit Card Users	Monthly Billings Proof of payment	Updated payments on account balances. No overdue accounts.

DISCUSSION

Profile of Employees in Government Academic Institutions in Daet, Camarines Norte

The respondents' profiles were described by sex, age, marital status, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, number of times of credit availment, and number of years using credit cards. These data are presented in Tables 1 to 8.

Sex. Table 1 for the sex profile of the respondents shows that out of 100, 82 respondents or 82 percent are females as compared to the male with a frequency of 18 or 18 percent.

The data shows that the highest indicator of sex profile is female. This indicates that women make up the majority of employees with credit cards in educational sectors. It implies that they secure credit cards to facilitate spending and budgeting. Based on the result, it is essential to point out that in most households in Camarines Norte, women are in charge of budgeting their finances. Additional support was based on the statistical data provided by selected institutions. Based on the personnel headcount of the Camarines Norte State College in October 2023, the percentage of female employees in CNSC Main Campus and College of Education is 57.4 percent outnumbering the male employees with only 42.6 percent. On the contrary, the data given by the DepEd Camarines Norte is not presented by sex profile and cannot be determined.

Similar findings were observed based on the study conducted by Bongco and Abenes (2019); it was mentioned that the majority gender of teachers in the Philippines is female, comprising 89.58 percent in public elementary and 77.06 percent in public secondary schools. Based on the popular belief that women are more nurturing than men as the ideal candidates to fill the need for teaching. On the other perspective, in the United States (US), the legacy of teaching as a woman's profession remains deeply embedded (Eisenmann, 2017).

According to an article published by the Philippine Star and Agcaoili (2023), CCAP executive director Alex Ilagan believes that credit cards increase women's purchasing capacity, stimulating consumer spending, which the economy requires to recover from the pandemic's aftermath. In addition, cardholders can receive immediate cash delivery in case of an emergency, which can be converted into an installment basis for ease of payment. They have access to credit, making it easier to handle their duties and manage their finances.

Age. Table 2 for the age profile of the respondents shows that out of the 100 respondents of government academic institutions in Daet, Camarines Norte, the age bracket with the highest frequency with the total of 36 or 36 percent of respondents are ages 31 to 40 while the age bracket with the lowest frequency with a total of 16 or 16

percent is age above 50. Also, the other brackets, 21 to 30 and 41 to 50, have the same frequency and percentage of 24 percent.

The data shows that most of the teachers using credit cards belong to the 31 to 40-year-old age group. This demonstrates that employees in this age range are confident and knowledgeable enough to use credit cards. At this stage, employees are more responsible as they develop in their careers and as individuals, considering the positive and negative aspects of using a credit card and how to manage their funds. They understand how to manage and allocate finances while keeping within their credit limits.

The lowest credit card users are from the age group above 50, as they are most conservative in spending. They are more inclined to utilize conventional payment methods, such as cash since they are reluctant to use credit cards or electronic payments.

Parallel to the findings of OECD's (2014) published article, employment rates reveal that those aged 25 to 54 are in their prime working years, while people aged 55 to 64 have reached the height of their careers and are approaching retirement. Also, Hutchison et al. (2016) emphasize that during adulthood, social-emotional development intersects with identity, morals, and job growth in dynamic ways that predict future views and lifestyle choices. Similarly, the study by Uddin (2019) mentioned that the age group above 50 are less likely to take an advance on credit cards. This is why people over 50 have a lower frequency of use and a lower chance of using credit cards for payment.

Marital Status. Table 3 corresponds to the marital status of the respondents and shows that the highest percentage using credit cards is already married, with a frequency of 64 percent. In comparison, the lowest percentage is 2 percent for annulled/legally separated respondents. The other bracket shows 30 percent and 4 percent for single and widowed respondents, respectively.

The data shows that most government academic institution employees are already married. This is supported by Table 2 results, wherein most teachers are 31 to 40 years of age. In this era, most employees have their own families, and married couples are expected to be more responsible in setting a budget for their family expenses to have a comfortable way of living. They must monitor their expenses and have an additional source of funds to augment their cash shortage in case of emergencies.

Shamardi (2017) corroborated the study's findings when they discovered that married credit card holders in Malaysia are more likely to be credit card reliant than single or separated/divorced persons. This might be because married customers spend more than non-married users, and household debt is highly related to family size. This demonstrates the necessity of paying more considerable living costs using the most convenient method, which is to utilize credit cards.

The lowest result falls under annulled/legally separated. It is because the Filipino culture still prevails as it is deeply rooted in their roots to value the sanctity of marriage. The Philippines is the only country in the world, together with the Vatican, where divorce

is illegal. If a married couple decides to separate ways, they can only petition for annulment of marriage or legal separation, not divorce. It indicates that a small proportion of credit card users have been annulled or legally separated.

It is supported by Surekha et al. (2022), the study found that separated individuals had a minor percentage of 2.3 percent on credit card utilization and convenience. The preceding conclusion indicates that most respondents are married; hence, it was found that most respondents are married since most young people have an affordable salary.

Highest Educational Attainment. As shown in Table 4, the respondents' highest educational attainment in academic institutions out of 100 responses, the employees with units in masters program have the highest frequency and percentage of 43 percent; the second is the college graduate with 34 percent, the third is the master degree holder with 15 percent, the fourth is with units in doctorate program with six percent, and lastly, doctorate degree holder with 2 per cent. Some choices have zero frequency, such as elementary graduate, high school graduate, master's degree (CAR), and doctoral degree (CAR).

The table shows the highest educational attainment among college graduates and doctorate degree holders. It is assumed that having a bachelor's degree makes them more likely to become financially literate and responsible in their financial decisions regarding loans and debts. However, possessing MBA units or a master's degree will provide advantages and credit points for qualifications, and it becomes a professional ladder for them to get promoted.

Credit card users, in terms of education attainment, primarily have units in master's programs. Most of the respondents, as teachers and faculty of academic institutions, enroll in master's degree programs to continue their studies after graduating with their bachelor's degrees and getting hired by their respective agencies. Academic institutions require applicants and employees to have finished at least a master's degree to be permanent in higher education institutions, per the Civil Service Commission. At the same time, it is a plus factor for promotion and administrative positions in the Department of Education.

In support of the findings, under the relevant provisions of Republic Act (RA) No. 7722, also known as the Higher Education Act of 1994, and under 297th Commission en banc Resolution No. 319 - 07 dated May 7, 2007, the addendum to CMO 30, series of 2004 entitled "Revised Policies and Standards for Undergraduate Teacher Education Curriculum," teaching at the tertiary level often requires a master's degree in education or a related area.

On the other hand, the lowest frequency of educational attainment is doctorate degree holders. Only a few of the respondents in the educational sector have completed their doctorate degrees because of the workloads and outputs that are supposedly complied with, along with the tasks and duties as teachers with instruction and designations to perform. In contrast, others are already contented with complying with the

minimum requirements to be permanent and no other goals to hold higher designations like principals or supervisors.

Parallel to the study of Castello et al. (2017), the most frequent motives for considering dropping out were difficulties in achieving a balance between work, personal life, and doctoral studies and problems with socialization. Because achieving a doctoral degree represents a commitment to achieving greater goals.

Monthly Gross Income. Table 5 shows the data in connection with the respondents' profile in terms of monthly income. Income below ₱30,000.00 has a higher frequency and percentage of 54 percent, while the lowest frequency and percentage of 7 percent falls under ₱50,001 to ₱100,000. The other brackets are ₱30,001 to ₱50,000 with frequency and percentages of 39 percent. Also, the gross monthly income with zero respondents amounts to ₱100,001.00 to ₱500,000.00 and above ₱500,000.00. The bracketing of gross monthly income is based on the bracket used by the banks from below ₱30,000.00 up to above ₱500,000.00.

The data shows that the majority of the educational sector employees have a salary below ₱30,000.00. This means that the majority of credit card users hold entry-level positions or fall under salary grade 11 and below. The positions with salary grade 11 and below are the following: administrative aide, teacher 1, supply officer, registrar, accounting staff, school health personnel, etc.

It is corroborated by Zoleta (2023), who stated that salary, benefits, and other sources of income influence minimum and maximum credit limits in the Philippines. A high salary increases the likelihood of receiving a large credit card limit. Most of the respondents are with lower positions or rank and equivalent of Salary Grades 10 to 12 ranging from Php 21,129.00 to ₱29,165.00, which are the Administrative Aide II, Teachers I and II, Guidance Counselors, Accountant, etc.

On the contrary, the lowest frequency and percentage of 8 percent are ₱50,001 to ₱100,000 monthly gross income equivalent to salary grades 19 to 25, representing higher positions in educational sectors such as principals, head teachers, supervisors, associate professors, professors, etc. The same result was established in the study of Shamardi (2017), which found that the senior teacher's segment with the highest salary bracket represents about 13.4 percent of the respondents. This signifies that most teachers, even though they have a higher source of income, do not want to use credit cards as part of their payment method. Most of the high-earners use cash or debit cards as a mode of payment.

Employment Status. Table 6 shows the data that the highest frequency and percentage of 49 percent is under permanent (teaching) employees using credit cards. In comparison, the lowest is under Job Order (JO) status with a frequency and percentage of 4 percent. The other bracket has 41 percent and 6 percent under permanent (non-teaching) and Contract of Service (COS), respectively.

The data shows that most government employees with credit cards are teaching personnel with permanent status. Permanent status pertains to the specific employment the respondents hold, which will remain until they retire, with the appropriate perks and advantages. It implies that they are already confident about availing of credit card benefits and privileges as they have the security of tenure.

It is congruent with the statistical data provided by the Department of Education Camarines Norte and Camarines Norte State College; the total number of teaching staff is 1,115, or 72 percent of the total population, while non-teaching personnel is 428, or 28 percent. In addition, based on the April 2020 statistics released by the Department of Education and the study of Llego (2020), DepEd Region V (Bicol) has a total number of 71,716 employees. The percentage of employment status is as follows: teaching with 65,699 or 92 percent, non-teaching with 4,171 or 6 percent, and job order/contract of service with 1,846 or 2 percent.

The lowest is the job order status with 4 percent. The lowest corresponds to hiring for intermittent positions that last little more than six months and are paid on a daily or hourly basis. It means that they do not have security of tenure and are more likely to be replaced after the contract or can change their jobs. It is corroborated by the report of the Presidential Communications Office (2024) as of June 30, 2023, 29.68 percent or a total of 832,812 of the government workforce were COS and JO workers. The Department of Education (DepEd) has a total of 15,143 COS/JO employees, with a percentage of 1.82 percent of the total population. This signifies that COS/JO employees have a small fraction in academic sectors and most have regular status.

Frequency of Credit Card Availment. Table 7 shows that the frequency and percentage of terms of credit card availment under the bracket of 1 to 3 times of availment per month is the highest, with a total of 87 percent. It is followed by 4 to 6 times per month with 6 percent, 10 and above per month with 5 percent, and lastly, 7 to 9 times per month with 2 percent being the lowest.

The table shows that the highest frequency of credit card availment is from brackets 1 to 3 times per month. It has been found that government personnel in the educational sector use their credit cards prudently and reasonably. Although they have the lowest credit card usage each month, which limits them from fully grasping the benefits, perks, rewards, other features, and ease of having a credit card, they know the importance of using it prudently. Credit cards are usually used to pay for groceries, monthly utilities and bills, and purchase needed items or necessities online or in traditional stores.

In support of this finding, even though there is no standardized minimum frequency of credit card use, experts recommend utilizing the card at least once every six months or, to be safe, once every three months, especially if the cards are retail credit cards (Harkness, 2022). Similarly, the Statista Research Department (2022) found that 37 percent of respondents used credit cards many times a week, while 8 percent said they seldom. The Credit Card Association of the Philippines estimates that there will be 7.5

million Filipino credit card users by March 2023. They also claimed that in the first three months of the year, they were able to issue approximately 12 million cards nationally.

The remaining brackets are 4 to 6 times, 7 to 9 times, and 10 and above per month, respectively. Only a few of the respondents utilize the full potential of credit cards as they use them more often. On the other hand, the application and use of credit cards always depend on the consumer's purpose in using them. This means that these are the users who are already at ease using them and fully realize the benefits.

Pokora's (2024) study shows that less than 10 percent of Americans use cash to pay for purchases based on Forbes Advisor Survey (2023). Debit cards and credit cards are the primary payment methods used, with 53 percent using a physical or virtual debit card and 37 percent using a physical or virtual credit card. More than a third of respondents (35 percent) mostly utilize credit cards to earn rewards. Other common reasons include a credit card being safer to carry around than cash (33 percent) and to cover expenses that cannot be afforded (28 percent). Also, utilizing a credit card varies widely between generations. Gen Z, with 41 percent and Millennials with 40 percent are more likely to use credit cards to establish credit. In comparison, Baby Boomers like credit cards because they are safer than cash 43 percent and to receive incentives 40 percent.

Number of Years Using Credit Cards. Table 8 below exhibits the number of years the employees used their credit cards. The bracket with the highest frequency and percentage is below one year, with a total of 44 percent; second is 1 to 5 years, with a total of 35 percent; third is above 10 years, with a total of 12 percent; and the lowest frequency and percentage, 9 percent, is under 6 to 10 years of using a credit card.

The data shows that government employees in academic institutions have been using credit cards for one year or less. It implies that they are new users who are still learning to use and maximize its benefits. Similarly, banking institutions continue to promote credit cards and cashless transactions, resulting in increased usage. As a result, the number of individuals who use credit cards in Camarines Norte is increasing.

New customers apply for credit cards for a variety of reasons, including the increasing number of establishments accepting card payments for transactions and convenience. It is substantiated by the report of Asian Banking and Finance (2023) that according to CCAP's quarterly survey of its 17 member issuers, the total number of credit cards issued in the Philippines was 11.8 million by the end of March. This signifies that the increase in credit card users is from the new applicants who attempt to have credit cards and that most of the respondents are new credit card holders.

On the other hand, the respondents with the lowest results are 6 to 10 years of using credit cards. Similarity was found in the study of Mohd Dali (2014), the lowest bracket in terms of the number of years using credit cards is approximately 28% of the respondents who have been using credit cards for six to ten years. According to other government employees, many cancel their credit cards due to reckless spending and poor budgeting that exceeds their planned budget. Most of them are unable to regulate when

they use their credit cards. Also, because they have not paid or have paid only the minimum due amount, they are required to pay compounded due amounts plus monthly interest.

Level of Credit Card Accessibility of Employees in Government Academic Institutions

The researcher studies the level of credit card accessibility in terms of the following variables: credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit. Ten indicators per variable are used to quantify respondents' level of credit card accessibility. The results are presented in Tables 9 to 11.

Credit Usage. Table 9 shows that the overall weighted mean in terms of credit usage is 3.25, which can be interpreted as being fully/highly accessible (FA). This indicator shows that credit cards can be accepted for payment in stores and merchants. It can be used as an alternative to cash payment with the highest weighted mean of 3.44 and 3.39, respectively, which are fully/highly accessible (FA). In contrast, it can be used to pay for utilities such as water bills, electric bills, internet, etc., and to secure mobile payments and contactless transactions. It has the lowest mean of 2.97 and 3.13, respectively, and is primarily accessible (MA).

Based on the representation in Table 9, after the data was consolidated and assessed, it proved that the respondents' level of credit card accessibility had been attained using the credit usage indicators. The highest indicator is that credit cards are accepted as payment by authorized merchants and stores; as the number of merchants accepting credit card payments progresses, there is an increasing need for more convenient forms of payment that leverage technological advancements. Credit cards are perhaps the most utilized sort of credit today, allowing customers to purchase nearly anything on credit. Then there is the usage of cards: credit cards provide users with access to a line of credit with no fees and digital payments (FinSMEs, 2021). They can also use a credit card to make purchases without taking out a personal loan and withdraw cash advances.

Furthermore, credit card customers can purchase items and work as a cash alternative. As a result, it helps both parties more than collecting cash and change. It prevents cash shortages and theft. It reduces the amount of cash that customers bring to the grocery store or use to make payments. This implies that credit cards may be used as an alternative to cash at any time and from any authorized merchants and businesses in the area that accept card payments.

The theoretical model proposed by Chen et al. (2018) predicts that customers use cash to pay for low-value purchases because it is relatively simple. However, the weight of coins restricts the convenience they get as they change. The major inconvenience of currency use, the necessity to carry metal coins in one's wallet, has remained practically unchanged for hundreds, if not thousands, of years. Conversely, there is a low outcome when respondents use their cards to pay for utilities such as water, power, and internet

bills. It implies that merchants, where customers pay for utilities, do not accept credit cards as a mode of payment. According to the conversations with PrimeWater and CANORECO personnel, credit cards are not accepted as a payment option. Although particular utility billers in the province do not take credit cards, there has been considerable growth in merchants and retailers that accept card payments; this is a good sign to improve credit card usage and accessibility in Daet, Camarines Norte.

Moreover, using credit cards to protect mobile payments and contactless transactions does not reduce accessibility. It indicates that people use credit cards for various payments, such as card reading at point-of-sale terminals. Moving from cash to digital payments may result in increased payment efficiency. Digital payment instruments such as e-money accounts, debit cards, credit cards, and prepaid cards are becoming increasingly popular, according to Delos Reyes et al. (2021). Brown (2021) also mentions the development of new payment technology, devices and channels which has drastically transformed the way customers make payments, particularly in the last five years.

Benefits and Advantages. Table 10 shows the overall weighted mean of benefits and advantages, which is 3.12 and can be interpreted as primarily accessible (MA). The indicator credit cards can source additional fund/s in emergencies or unexpected situations. It can increase the allowable credit limit, and credit score has the highest weighted mean of 3.31 and 3.27, respectively, which is fully/highly accessible (FA).

In contrast, the indicator can cover benefits on travels or special offers such as travel insurance in case of loss, damage, or stolen/fraud. It can offer minimal or up to free of charge on an annual fee and has the lowest mean of 2.89 and 2.96, respectively, which is primarily accessible (MA).

The table shows that most respondents recognize the benefits and advantages of credit cards, including the ability to utilize them as a source of additional cash in an emergency or unanticipated problem. It indicates that credit cards can be beneficial for credit card users in emergencies where cash can be acquired through the cash advance feature of credit cards, as it can assist them in augmenting their cash shortages and pay on an installment basis. Although cash advances have additional fees upon withdrawal, credit cards greatly help users efficiently use funds hassle-free from loan applications. The study by Gupta (2017) supported the findings that credit cards have been beneficial in the past few years by allowing users to get loans if they do not have enough money in an emergency. To avoid charges, it must guarantee that repayments are made on time. Credit card limits are not hampered; therefore, they can be used to deal with emergencies.

In addition, the credit card provider approves an increase in the acceptable credit limit and credit score. Respondents are provided with information regarding the advantages of higher credit limits and credit scores. It signifies that increasing credit limits significantly impacts credit card users' accessibility since it enhances their purchasing power when using credit cards. Most new credit card users have a minimum credit limit of Php 20,000.00, which increases over time based on their usage and payment history, as well as the bank's credit evaluations to check their financial situation and reputation

and determine an acceptable credit limit. Credit card users responsible for their spending and having adequate money to cover their monthly payments would benefit the most from a credit limit increase (Zoleta,2023).

Even though with the lowest weighted mean, the coverage of benefits on travels or special offers such as travel insurance in case of loss, damage, or stolen/fraud. The least common concern for users is using credit cards for payments. It denotes that users are not concerned with travel benefits or special offers, as they do not use credit cards for travel purposes. On the other hand, consider the benefits and advantages such as purchase/warranty protection and security while traveling (American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, 2023). The users must know that using a credit card involves risk. However, there are numerous instances in which it makes sense to use a credit card instead of cash, such as for convenience, card benefits, security, or rewards.

Initially, security concerns limited the use of credit cards for online payments. However, as more secure features were added to ensure the safety of every transaction, consumers gained assurance in using credit cards. The applicability of credit cards is a significant contributor to their global prevalence. The security against fraud offered by credit cards may be the primary justification for using them rather than cash or debit cards, Lake (2023). There has been an increase in advocacy initiatives for responsible credit card use and enhanced cardholder protection (Credit Card Association of the Philippines (CCAP), 2021).

Furthermore, the benefit of minimal or no annual fee is less likely to dissuade users from keeping credit cards. However, it might be a massive advantage for them in reducing the card's costs. It implies that paying reasonable fees does not influence the purpose of using the credit card. According to Pokora (2023), the card's entire cost and advantages. After considering increased rewards and desirable features, a credit card with an annual fee may be advantageous. However, if unable to find an easy means to offset a card's annual fee, users might want to explore a cheaper alternative.

Terms of Credit. Table 11 shows the overall weighted mean of the respondents under the level of credit card accessibility in terms of credit, which is 3.24, which can be interpreted as primarily accessible (MA), ranging from 2.50-3.24. Indicator number 5, "Can provide details on purchase transactions and payments", and number 4, "Can access or view the statement of account through digital channels (email, SMS, etc.)", with the highest weighted mean of 3.38 and 3.35, respectively, and interpreted as fully/highly accessible (FA) together with indicator number 9. The other indicators interpreted as most accessible (MA) are indicator numbers 1, 2, 3, 6, and 7, and with the lowest weighted mean is indicator number 10, "Can provide fast and hassle-free approval of credit card applications" and number 8, "Can secure approval of the credit card application without collateral" with a weighted mean of 3.14 and 3.18, respectively.

In connection with the level of credit card accessibility of the respondents in terms of credit, it covers the following: the interest rates, collaterals, documentation and requirements, and mode of payments. The indicator with the highest weighted mean

demonstrates that giving data on purchased transactions and payments improves credit card accessibility; while using credit cards, the respondents have complete oversight over their spending history and transactions, allowing them to manage their finances better more effectively.

It is supported by the study of Chen (2022), which implies that providing details of transactions and payments helps the user monitor their spending routine. Credit card users may stay on budget by maintaining records and monitoring their credit utilization. Users may verify if there have been any modifications to their credit record and take corrective action on time.

In addition, accessing and viewing the statement of account through online channels enable individuals to keep track of their transactions and understand their spending habits. Credit card users need to monitor their transactions online to avoid the inconvenience of going to the credit card issuer to request the statement of account. This means that aside from going to the issuers, the users can easily access, view, or download statements of accounts at their convenience.

According to BSP (2023), a bank statement is a summary of all transactions for a bank account during a specific period, usually monthly. It covers deposits, charges, withdrawals, and the period's beginning and ending balances. Account holders typically review their bank statements to keep track of their expenses and spending and check for any fraudulent charges or mistakes. Providing fast and straightforward credit card approval has a minor negative effect on credit card accessibility and credit terms. Applying for a credit card is not as simple as opening a savings account. It demonstrates that they will wait until their credit card is released. On the other hand, card issuers like banks have pre-approved credit cards ready for activation for their customers with existing deposits and good tracking records. This process saves time and effort for the users to have a credit card, and it is easier to activate and use.

However, some credit card issuers take some time to complete and undertake extensive credit and background checks before the application is approved. The main reason is that credit card approval periods are influenced by the creditworthiness, the issuer's regulations, and the complexity of their application. To successfully handle the credit card acceptance process, keep good credit habits, select the best card for your financial circumstances, and remain patient. If the credit card application takes time, there may be an influx of credit applications, extending the time it takes for the issuer to process the applications. Furthermore, the card issuer may want further information from the applicants to validate their personal information and other data (Johnson & Zimmer, 2024).

Applying for a credit card does not need collateral; nonetheless, credit card users have to enhance their creditworthiness and maintain an excellent track record of payments in order to be granted the highest possible credit limit. It conveys that they are not required to provide any collateral to have their request for an increase in credit limit, and it does not affect their credit card accessibility. According to the report of Bangko

Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) (2023), applying for a loan from a bank was considered the most difficult (65 percent), followed by credit card companies (56 percent), online lenders (48 percent), cooperatives/NSSLAs (47 percent), and financing/lending companies (44 percent). The top reasons formal institutions gave for perceived difficulty in borrowing were a lack of documentary requirements, insufficient IDs, a low salary/income, and a lack of collateral. The applicants need more time and patience.

Significant Relationship between the Profile of Employees in Government Academic Institutions and the Level of Credit Card Accessibility

The test for significant relationships that may exist between the profile of the government employees in academic institutions along sex, age, marital status, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, frequency of credit availment, and the number of years of using a credit card and the level of credit card accessibility in terms of credit usage, benefits and advantages and terms of credit were tested using Somer's Delta Correlation (d) and the Contingency Coefficient (C). Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient was used between the profiles, including age, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, frequency of availment and number of years using credit cards, and the level of credit card accessibility in the three variables. Additionally, the Contingency Coefficient was used to compare the profiles regarding sex, marital status, employment status, and the level of credit card accessibility under the variables considered.

Table 12 shows that significant relationships exist on the profile in terms of age ($d=-.268$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) and marital status ($C= .440$, $p\text{-value}=.004$), both at 0.01 level when paired to the level of credit card accessibility along with credit usage. The result of a significant relationship between age and credit usage can be interpreted as older individuals having an already established financial position, which reduces the need for credit card usage. This finding is supported in the report of Hurd (2023), that baby boomers (those who were born between 1946 and 1964) only have 4.8 percent in the second quarter of 2019 compared with other age brackets; the reason for this is older adults had a less income in which one of the criteria to approved in credit card was the income.

The result also indicates that older individuals may prefer the traditional modes of payment or may have lower risk tolerance than younger individuals. This was supported by the report of Thompson (2024) in which, according to the study, baby boomers (born 1946-1964) this was the generation who were attached to the traditional ways where they shop and paid on a cash basis compared with other generations like Millennials this generation more likely to use technology and online transactions like credit cards. Moreover, the significant relationship between marital status and credit usage indicates a positive, moderately strong relationship, and the $p\text{-value}$ also suggests that this relationship is statistically significant. It suggests that married individuals are more likely to use credit cards than unmarried individuals.

This finding aligns with the notion that married individuals may have significantly higher expenses, necessitating the use of credit cards. This was supported by Beck and Petry (2022), the study found that people who are married usually have a higher income than single individuals because of their combined income; however, due to other factors that need to be considered, such as educational expenses and allowances for their child and food, married couples are usually spending more than single individuals. Because of the additional expenses associated with parental duties, married couples sought a credit card.

On the other hand, profiles such as sex, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, frequency of avancement, and number of years using the credit card did not obtain a significant relationship with credit usage. The lack of a significant relationship between sex and credit usage indicates that sex, whether male or female, does not have a direct impact on an individual's credit card accessibility and usage.

Likewise, the employees' educational attainment does not directly influence the individual's credit card usage. The absence of a significant relationship indicates that individuals with different educational levels have similar credit card usage behavior. Moreover, the lack of a significant relationship between monthly income and credit usage implies that individuals with different gross monthly incomes have similar credit card usage behavior. Similarly, employment status does not play a significant role in determining an individual's credit usage behavior. The same results were also obtained in terms of frequency of avancement and number of years using the credit card. The mentioned profiles are not predictors of credit card usage, meaning they are not directly related to the card usage behavior of government employees in academic institutions.

The table also reveals that there is a significant relationship between the level of credit card accessibility along with benefits and advantages and the profile of the employees in terms of age ($d=-.195$, $p\text{-value}=.006$) and marital status ($C=.461$, $p\text{-value}=.001$) both at 0.01 level. The negative correlation coefficient in age indicates that as age increases, credit card accessibility to benefits and advantages tends to decrease. This suggests that younger employees are more likely to have higher levels of credit card accessibility and enjoy more benefits and advantages. On the other hand, older employees are more likely to have lower levels of credit card accessibility. They may not have as many benefits and advantages associated with their credit cards.

This was supported by Bareham and Carrasquillo (2024), who stated that to enjoy credit card rewards and benefits such as high credit points, credit holders should spend more frequently using their credit cards. If a person utilized a credit card in the early years, they would have an advantage over those who had just started. Old cardholders accumulate points and enjoy credit card advantages more than new cardholders.

Similarly, the significant relationship between marital status and benefits and advantages suggests that married employees are more likely to have higher levels of credit card accessibility and enjoy more benefits and advantages. It signifies that marital

status affects the use of credit cards; the frequency of usage adjusts as they change their marital status. It is concluded that married couples are more likely to use credit cards than single, widowed, and separated individuals.

In support Empeople Credit Union and Brosnan (2024), five of the financial troubles in marriage are due to the burden of duty, as the married couple failed to control their monthly spending. One of the benefits and advantages of credit cards is that issuing banks always disclose a statement of account every month, enabling cardholders to review the history of their credit card spending. Furthermore, one of the problems married people face is finding a source of additional funds in a fortuitous event; this is one of the benefits of credit cards, as credit card holders can make cash advances at any time using their credit card.

Other profiles such as sex, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, frequency of avilment, and number of years using credit cards are not significantly correlated along benefits and advantages. This suggests that the employees' profiles above do not significantly influence the benefits and advantages they may derive from their credit cards. Moreover, these profile variables do not play a significant role in determining individuals' benefits and advantages from their credit cards. Finally, a significant relationship exists between the level of credit card accessibility and terms of credit and the profile, age, and marital status. The table shows that terms of credit and age obtained a coefficient of $d=-.274$ with a p-value of .000 at 0.01 level. Thus, it indicates a negative correlation, and the p-value is statistically significant. The result indicates that older employees may have a high level of credit card accessibility on terms of credit due to factors such as perceived higher risk associated with older individuals, as they may have limited income or are closer to retirement.

Alternatively, it may result in older individuals having established credit histories and lower credit utilization, leading to shorter-term credit. This was confirmed by Smith (2016), who stated that one of the elements of credit terms was the mode of payment, which allows cardholders to extend or decrease the duration of credit repayment. Banks benefit from longer credit periods. However, older individuals prefer short-term credit. As people became older, they wanted to avoid dealing with issues such as loans that needed to be paid, therefore they had decreased credit utilization.

Likewise, the coefficient for marital status and terms of credit is $C=.387$, with a p-value of 0.04 at a 0.05 level. This means that a positive relationship exists between the variables considered, and the p-value of 0.04 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant. This result suggests that married individuals may have more favorable credit terms. This could be due to factors such as perceived stability and shared financial responsibility in marriage. This was supported by Cvetkovic and Bingler (2023), who stated that one of the qualifications of a credit card issuer is that the individual can afford to pay the account balances if they are applying for a credit card or at least make the minimum payments. As a result, the cardholder/applicants' income should be consistent or have a steady cash inflow for the card issuer to grant them a credit card. This was a

significant advantage of being married, as the husband and wife's combined income could have been leveraged to qualify for a credit card.

The other profile variables lack a significant relationship on the level of accessibility of credit cards along terms of credit. The level of accessibility of credit cards along terms of credit has nothing to do with the profile of government employees in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, gross monthly income, employment status, frequency of avancement, and number of years using the credit card. Thus, these profile variables are not considered predictors of the level of accessibility along terms of credit. Generally, the study's null hypothesis will not be rejected except for the profile variables such as age and marital status.

Problems Encountered by Employees of Government Academic Institutions in Accessing the Credit Card Facility

In this study, the researchers identified problems encountered by credit card users. Each variable identified five (5) problems that the users encountered with credit card accessibility. The problems are ranked based on the frequency per problem that the respondents selected based on their experience and knowledge about credit card accessibility. Most respondents did not have other suggestions or recommendations besides the problems identified. The results of the survey are in Tables 13 to 15.

Credit Usage. Table 13 represents the problems encountered by employees in accessing the credit card facility along with credit usage with the indicators; "Limited merchant's payment options" with the highest frequency of 52 responses; second, "poor signal and internet connection" with 40 responses; third, "No available Point-of-Sale (POS) system" with 32 responses; fourth, "Prolonged troubleshooting and unresolved customer complaints" with 18 responses, and last, "No available card replacement on expired and damaged card" with 16 responses.

Even though there are positive contributions to credit card usage, every user experiences problems that need to be resolved. The table shows that the limited merchant payment options have the highest frequency identified by the users as a problem using the credit card. This indicates that a limited number of merchants and establishments accept card payments, especially credit cards. It has been a challenge for credit card users to figure out where to use their cards when so few shops accept them. The result in Table 9 identifies the level of credit card accessibility that can be used to pay for utilities such as water bills, electric bills, and internet, among others, implying that the most common problem encountered by credit card users is the limited payment options. Unfortunately, as of April 2024, CANORECO and PrimeWater are not accepting credit card payments for utility bill transactions in Camarines Norte.

On the other hand, as the economy keeps growing, more companies and merchants, including SM enterprises, grocery stores, hypermarkets, and other food chains, accept credit card payments. However, in previous years, few shopping malls, department stores, or establishments accepted credit cards in Daet, Camarines Norte.

In a similar finding, Felt et al. (2020) reported that most retailers accept all three methods, and debit and credit card acceptance varies depending on business size and industry. Credit card payments are often the most expensive of the three ways, as businesses must pay significant interchange fees to card issuers for each transaction. Unfortunately, most companies that do not accept credit cards are smaller and serve a population that prefers cash or may have difficulty setting up a merchant account and other technology-based financial services due to a lack of internet access.

The lowest indicator is no available card replacement on expired and damaged cards. This implies that replacing expired and damaged cards has not become an issue for users. Credit card companies send an information letter before the card expires to confirm renewal, whereas some issuers automatically renew cards for reactivation before the expiration dates. If the card has been damaged or compromised by fraudulent transactions, report it immediately and call customer service or submit a complaint at the nearest branch of accounts for replacements.

In support, Ferraro (2023) points out that in most cases, the bank will instantly generate a replacement card and ship it within a few days. If not, contact their customer support and seek a renewal.

Benefits and Advantages. Table 14 represents the problems employees encounter in accessing the credit card facility, along with benefits and advantages. The indicator with the highest frequency is “susceptible to fraud and unauthorised transactions”, with 43 responses; second, “low available credit limit”, with 39 responses; third, “no rewards and warranty on purchase items” with 22 responses; and last are indicators with the same number of respondents, “no available online payment options (over-the-counter payment)” and “high level of salary bracket and income requirements” with both 21 responses. This signifies that most of the respondents are concerned with the security of their accounts, which is a common issue for older employees who are more likely conservative customers.

The table shows that the most prevalent challenge consumers have in terms of benefits and advantages is that they are concerned that their credit cards may be susceptible to fraud or unauthorized transactions. Credit card fraud occurs when someone else uses a credit card (or debit card) to make a transaction or withdraw cash without permission from the cardholder. It is characterized as identity theft since scammers use personal information and credentials to initiate transactions. This issue has a negative effect on using credit cards since people are afraid of fraud and unauthorized transactions, as well as being charged for products they did not purchase. It is one of the reasons why credit card issuers strive to raise awareness about credit card fraud and how to prevent it.

In parallel research, credit card theft soared considerably in 2022, as reported by Forbes Advisor's Underwood (2023) study. According to the Federal Trade Commission (FTC), fraud complaints for new accounts grew by over 13 percent, while fraud on existing accounts increased by more than 23 percent. On the other hand, according to Visa, credit card fraud in the Philippines will reach an all-time low by 2023. But this is not an excuse

to be complacent; it is still an obligation to remain attentive and protect yourself against fraudulent individuals. To keep cyber criminals away, the owner may take several safeguards, the most essential of which is understanding how to use credit cards responsibly, Pagkatotohan (2023). Credit card users must take proactive steps to protect their personal and financial information, be vigilant, and be aware of how to recognize fraudulent transactions. Users can establish strong password combinations, examine account statements regularly, and notify credit card issuers of questionable behavior.

There are many ways to avoid being a victim of credit card fraud, such as opting for branch pickup, signing a credit card, considering your credit card as crucial as cash, not putting all cards in one location, shredding anything with credit card information on it, do not sign blank receipts, check credit card statements, be wary of phone transactions, do not lend credit cards, keep credit card in view when paying, never post credit card details online, only shop at trustworthy websites, review app permissions on mobile, use card only at trustworthy locations, avoid using public wi-fi, never share CVC, and destroy expired physical card (Underwood, 2023).

The indicators with the lowest rankings include no available online payment options (only over-the-counter payments) and high levels of salary bracket and income requirements. The low frequency of the indicator no available online payment options (only over-the-counter payments) reflects that, while it has been noted as a problem, it does not influence users' accessibility. One of the positive contributions of the pandemic was the improvement and enhancement of digital banking products, where customers can transfer funds and make payments in real time. They can pay their credit card bills at authorized agents such as SM Bayad Centers and even through Gcash Pay or Maya Pay with minimal fees instead of going to the banks. According to Zoleta (2023), banks provide a broad range of credit card payment options for the convenience of their customers. With so many alternatives accessible today, it has become easier for cardholders to pay their credit cards on schedule. Furthermore, high salary and income requirements have minimal impact on credit card accessibility. Based on the statistical data, income requirement has no significant relationship with the level of credit card accessibility. Even though it is one of the most critical factors in granting a credit card application, the applicant must have an established source of income. Some credit card issuers offer minimal salary requirements up to Php 120,000.00 per year or Php 10,000.00 monthly, considering that the user's gross monthly income falls below Php 30,000.00. This means that despite their low income, individuals can apply for credit cards to benefit from using credit.

The product features will differ based on the type of credit card that most appropriately fits their budget and lifestyle. In addition to DeNicola's (2024) article, credit card applications request annual or monthly income in addition to contact details and household expenditures. Card issuers consider this information, as well as credit reports and credit scores when deciding whether to approve an application. They also use the information to determine if they can afford an additional credit card payment. Card issuers are responsible for evaluating cardholders' capacity to pay when issuing new cards or increasing credit limits.

Terms of Credit. Table 15 represents the problems employees encounter in accessing the credit card facility along with terms of credit. The indicator with the highest frequency, “high interest rates and charges”, with a total of 48 responses; the second “, fees on missed payments/late payment”, with 46 responses”; the third “, failure to repay account balances or minimum due amount” with 27 responses, the fourth “untimely posting of purchased and payment transactions” with 17 responses, and lastly “Complicated terms and conditions” with 13 responses.

The table shows that the most common concerns among credit card users are high interest rates and charges. On the other hand, the level of credit card accessibility, which can offer a reasonable interest rate per type of account, has a low result and is interpreted as primarily accessible in Table 11. This means that the interest rates and charges affect the level of credit card accessibility and mostly the problems that credit card users encounter. In contrast, credit card issuers earned income by charging fees to credit card users and adding extra charges for each payment default. However, it only applies when consumers do not pay the whole amount due for the month, and there is an excess that will be carried over to the following billing cycle. Credit card interest rates can be avoided by updating your balance before the following billing cycle.

Based on Investopedia's previous report (2024), the average credit card interest rate is 24.37 percent as of March 2024. The latest data from the association of 17 major credit card issuers in the Philippines showed that the delinquency rate further declined to 3.26 percent in the first quarter from 3.32 percent in the same period last year (Agcaoili, 2023).

Some claim that credit cards are complex and risky since banks charge high interest rates, potentially resulting in unmanageable debt. However, a popular misconception is that credit cards have a negative track record. Almost all credit cards charge interest solely if the payment is not paid in full each month; to avoid incurring additional interest and penalties, pay the balance due on or before the end of the billing cycle period. Settling the outstanding balance avoids any chance of incurring interest payments on account. It is about the user's spending habits and how they select and use credit cards. Suppose credit card balances rapidly increase and become unmanageable. In that case, it is critical to prioritize reducing or paying off debt and eliminating credit card interest payments all at once so that interest rates do not accumulate. Zoleta (2023) reiterates that paying off credit card debt every month represents prudent financial management, as it avoids exorbitant interest rates, and they genuinely do not believe that they will be able to pay off credit card payments every month and should create a budget and spend within their means to prevent getting into debt. Credit card issuers are assumed to explain the subject matter and essential information that credit card customers need to understand and are familiar with. The lowest frequency signifies that users are less likely to be concerned about terms and conditions when using a credit card as long as it benefits them and has no adverse effect on their budget or spending habits.

The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas Manual of Regulations for Banks (MORB) states that the general strategy in credit card operations is to guarantee that consumer credit is

readily accessible under fair and sound business standards consistent with global best practices. Likewise, Terrell et al. (2022) clarify that credit card terms and conditions are a legal agreement between the card issuer and the cardholder. Understanding the terms and conditions prepares the cardholder to use it safely and responsibly. Neglecting to follow the terms in your card agreement may result in penalties, fees, account termination, and other consequences.

Proposed Intervention to Improve the Credit Card Accessibility of Employees in Government Academic Institutions

The action plan's design is based on the captured responses on the problems encountered by employees of government academic institutions in accessing credit cards, along with the variables: credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit. This plays an important role in helping them maximize the purpose of having a credit card.

Proposed Intervention Plan to Improve Credit Card Accessibility. Table 17 presents the proposed intervention plan to improve credit card accessibility. The highlighted issues are based on the three problems with the highest frequencies encountered per variable. This will be the area of concern that this study will focus on to reduce the problem of credit card users regarding credit card accessibility. Identifying the objectives for the desired outcome and detailed strategies and techniques for accomplishing it. Goal setting is crucial because it identifies the techniques required to achieve the intended result. The resources needed are intangible or tangible materials. Finally, keep track of the projected outcome if the objectives are accomplished.

The table demonstrates the recommended intervention to improve credit card accessibility among employees of government academic institutions. The proposed interventions to resolve the problems along credit usage are as follows: (1) poor signal and internet connections to make sure that stores and merchants are online to avoid inconvenience and to have an uninterrupted mode of payment using credit cards; (2) limited merchants' payment option, to identify the stores and merchants that accept credit cards and maximize the utilization of credit card and availability as payment options; and (3) no available point-of-sale (POS) system, to identify stores/merchants with POS systems and ensure the availability to accept credit card payments.

Furthermore, the proposed interventions to resolve the problems along with benefits and advantages are as follows: (1) low available credit limit, to increase the allowable credit limit through improving credit history and avoid late payments in order to approve the increase on credit limit; (2) susceptible to fraud and unauthorized transactions, to avoid becoming victim of fraud and unauthorized transactions by establishing strong security passwords and not letting others use the personal credit card to have secured credit card transactions and ease of use; and (3) no rewards and warranty on purchase items, to maximize the benefits when using credit cards by exploring credit card offers such as rewards, bonuses, and warranty on purchases.

Moreover, the proposed interventions to resolve the problems along terms of credit: (1) high-interest rates and charges, to avoid additional interest rates and charges by paying the account balances in full per billing accounts; (2) fees on missed payments/late payments, to avoid additional charges on missed/late payments credit card users will conduct monitoring of amount dues and deadlines on billing statements and pay in full to avoid charges; and failure to repay account balances or minimum due amount, to avoid the rollover or compounding of account balances and interest charges they need to purchase base on their capacity to pay the account balances in total and update payments with no overdue amounts. The proposed intervention is presented for implementation to address the problems encountered by users in credit card accessibility, as well as to put into action the strategies recommended to achieve the objectives and expected outcomes to reduce users' problems in terms of credit card accessibility.

Findings

In connection with the result of the data gathered the following are the notable findings of the study:

1. The result of the survey from one hundred (100) respondents with credit cards from the educational sectors, the profile of the respondents shows that in terms of sex, they are predominantly female with frequency and percentage of 82 percent, with an age bracket of 31 to 40 years old with frequency and percentage of 36 percent, most of them are married with frequency and percentage of 64 percent, in terms of highest educational attainment 43 percent of them have units in a masters program, and 54 percent of the respondents have a monthly gross income of below Php 30,000.00, which are permanent (teaching) with frequency and percentage of 49 percent, they usually used credit card 1 to 3 times per month with frequency and percentage of 87 percent, and 44 percent of the respondent are using a credit card with below one (1) year.
2. The level of credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions was measured based on three variables and with an overall weighted mean and interpretation: credit usage has 3.25 which is fully/highly accessible, with the highest weighted mean of 3.44 as an indicator number 2, "Can be accepted for payment in stores and merchants" and the lowest weighted mean of 2.97, is indicator number 8, "Can be used to pay for utilities such as water bills, electric bills, internet, etc.; benefits and advantages have 3.12 which is mostly accessible, with indicator number 2 "Can be a source of additional fund/s in case of emergencies or unexpected situations" has the highest weighted mean of 3.31 and indicator number 10, "Can cover benefits on travels or special offers such as travel insurance in case of loss, damage, or stolen/fraud" has the lowest weighted mean of 2.89; and lastly, terms of credit have 3.24 which is mostly accessible with has the indicator with highest weighted mean of 3.38, "Can provide details on purchase transactions and payments" and the indicator with lowest weighted mean of 3.14, "Can provide fast and hassle-free approval of credit card applications".
3. The test for a significant relationship between the profile of the employees of government academic institutions and the level of credit card accessibility was

measured using Somer's Delta Correlation (d) and the Contingency Coefficient (C). The findings demonstrate that significant relationships exist on the profile in terms of age ($d=-.268$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) and married status ($C=.440$, $p\text{-value}=.004$), both at the 0.01 level when paired with the level of credit card accessibility along with credit usage. As compared to other characteristics, sex, greatest educational attainment, monthly gross income, work status, frequency of avilment, and number of years using the credit card did not display a significant relationship along credit usage.

Moreover, it displays a significant relationship between the level of credit card accessibility, along with benefits and advantages, and the employee profile in terms of age ($d=-.195$, $p\text{-value}=.006$) and married status ($C=.461$, $p\text{-value}=.001$), both at the 0.01 level. The negative correlation coefficient in age indicates that as the age of the person increases, the level of credit card accessibility, benefits, and advantages decreases. Other factors such as sex, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, employment status, frequency of avilment, and number of years using credit cards are not significantly correlated along benefits and advantages.

Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between the level of credit card accessibility along terms of credit and the profile along age and marital status. It shows that terms of credit and age obtained a coefficient of $d=-.274$ with $p\text{-value}$ of .000 at 0.01 level. Thus, there is a negative correlation and the $p\text{-value}$ is statistically significant. Similarly, the correlation coefficient for marital status and terms of credit is $C=.387$ with $p\text{-value}$ of 0.04 at 0.05 level. This suggests that there is a positive relationship exists between the variables considered and the $p\text{-value}$ of 0.04 indicates that the relationship is statistically significant. Meanwhile, the other profile variables show a lack of significant relationship with the level of accessibility of credit cards along terms of credit. The level of credit card accessibility on terms of credit has nothing to do with the profile of government employees along with sex, highest educational attainment, gross monthly income, employment status, frequency of avilment, and number of years using the credit card. As a result, these profile variables are not considered predictors of accessibility along terms of credit.

4. The research identified five (5) problems for each variable that the user encountered with credit card accessibility. The result focuses on the three problems that appear to have the highest frequency per variable. In terms of credit usage, "the limited merchant's payment options" ranked first with 52 responses, second was "poor signal and internet connection" with 40 responses, and third was: no available point-of-sale (POS) system" with 32 responses. In terms of benefits and advantages, "Susceptible to fraud and unauthorized transactions has 43 responses ranked first, "low available credit limit" with 39 responses ranked second, and "no rewards and warranty on purchase items" with 22 responses ranked third. Lastly, the terms of credit with the highest frequency of 48 responses, "high interest rates and charges", second with 46 responses "fees on missed payments/late payments", and third with 27 responses "failure to repay account balances or minimum due amount".

5. A proposed intervention is to address the problems encountered by credit card users, increase credit card accessibility, and optimize the benefits of acquiring a credit card. The proposed intervention plan will focus on addressing the issues identified by employees in order to improve credit card accessibility in Daet, Camarines Norte. By using the proposed strategy to accomplish the objectives and expected outcomes, credit card users' problems with credit card accessibility will be addressed.
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Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher observed the following conclusions:

1. Based on the findings, the profile of the respondents from the Department of Education and Camarines Norte State College - Main and Abaño Campus in Daet, Camarines Norte were mostly female, ranging in age from 31 to 40 years old, married, with units of master's program, with monthly gross income of below Php 30,000.00, employed as permanent (teaching), used credit cards 1 to 3 times per month, and had been using credit cards for less than one year.
2. The level of credit card accessibility of employees of government academic institutions was determined based on the weighted mean that was computed and interpreted as follows: credit usage was interpreted as fully/highly accessible with 3.25 WM, while credit benefits and advantages, and terms of credit were interpreted as mostly accessible with 3.12 and 3.24, respectively.
3. The level of credit card accessibility along with credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit established a significant relationship between the profile of the respondent in terms of age and marital status. However, other factors such as sex, highest educational attainment, monthly gross income, work status, frequency of availment, and number of years using the credit card are not significantly correlated along the credit usage, benefits and advantages, and terms of credit.
4. The problems encountered with the highest frequency that need to be addressed in this study to improve the credit card accessibility by the employees of government academic institutions per variables are the following: limited merchant's payment options, susceptibility to fraud and unauthorized transactions, and lastly, high interest rates and charges.
5. Based on the findings of the study, the formulated intervention plan was designed to resolve the problems encountered, increase the level of credit card accessibility, and optimize the benefits of credit cards by the end users. Utilizing the strategic response can accomplish the objectives and expected outcomes.

Recommendations

After the analysis and interpretation of data, here are the recommendations based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. Based on the conclusion, consider validating the demographic profile of credit card users from other government agencies and private companies, along with government academic institutions, it will broaden the scope of respondents' projection. Especially in terms of sex, some agencies are gender sensitive or have preferences in hiring employees. In terms of profile, future researchers may evaluate the respondents' gender rather than sex. Include lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual (LGBTQIA) options whenever possible for the study. Furthermore, respondents' employment status is assigned by their agency, with other agencies having more job orders or contracts for services than government academic institutions. Moreover, determine the total number of credit card users per agency and subsequently apply the other sampling technique that will capture the most responses to reduce the margin of error while obtaining a more accurate result.
2. To increase the level of credit card accessibility of the employees, the credit card companies may offer additional features or product improvements and innovations to implement that accept card payments in-store/merchants in Daet, Camarines Norte to promote credit card use. Credit card customers may utilize credit card payments on both POS terminals and online, giving them easy access to their purchases and transactions. In terms of credit, a complete marketing strategy that is in favor of the credit card users encourages and increases the utilization of credit cards through promotional incentives, points, and other perks such as no annual fees, a limited credit limit, installment plans, zero or low interest rates, and an easy application process.
3. Broaden the scope of the subject's data to include additional respondents. To collect further data on the demographic profile, particularly in terms of sex, greatest educational attainment, monthly gross income, job status, frequency of availment, and number of years using the credit card, in order to assess the significant relationships between variables and responses. Confirm the conclusion with the current study so that it may be utilized as a reference to compare the study's findings.
4. To address the issue of restricted merchant payment options, before making a payment, ensure that the merchant/store has a POS system. Encourages merchants/stores to install POS systems to increase the number of merchants that allow credit cards as a form of payment, giving customers additional payment alternatives and the ability to use credit cards when shopping online. Furthermore, credit card companies, banks, and other financial institutions may provide financial literacy orientations, particularly in credit management, in order to enhance government employees' credit behavior and knowledge of fraud and illegal transactions. The importance of spending wisely, using credit cards as payment methods, and paying in full on or before deadlines.
5. Disseminate the proposed intervention plan to the employees of academic institutions through conducting seminars and presentations in order to execute strategic solutions for the attainment of the objectives and expected outcomes to prevent problems that may arise while using credit cards as a payment method. Future researchers may do further studies to address problems that were overlooked in the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the initiation of the study, the researcher secured explicit informed consent from all participants. Formal request letters were submitted to the relevant government agencies, outlining the study's objectives and the researchers' commitment to ethical conduct. The letters emphasized the protection of participant rights, including data privacy and confidentiality. The researcher committed to conducting the study independently and free from any personal or financial interests that could influence the findings and to maintain strict adherence to academic integrity, ensuring that there was no plagiarism in the study. Upon careful review, the agencies granted their approval, facilitating the researchers' access to the target population. This approval was a crucial step in ensuring the study's legitimacy and ethical compliance.

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